

Constituents of the Leaves of *Vitex Negundo*.

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Vitex negundo, Linn., Vern. *Nishinda* (Beng.) *Samhalu* (Hindi), is common throughout India. Various medicinal properties are ascribed to the leaves and the roots of this plant in the Indian system of medicines. The leaves are said to be vermifuge and a tonic. The decoction of the leaves is given in catarrhal fever and the juice is used for removing foetid discharges and worms from ulcers (Kirtikar and Basu, "Indian Medicinal Plants" II, p. 999). Nothing was known about the constituents of the leaves to account for these medicinal properties, excepting that Broosma (Wehmer, "Planzen Stoffe" p. 647) has found a trace of an alkaloid in the leaves. It was, therefore, thought desirable to examine the constituents of the leaves in detail with a view to find out the active principles.

The mature leaves of the plant, collected in September and October, were first examined and an amorphous basic substance of an alkaloidable nature (0.03%) could be isolated. Since the amount present was very small, it was not examined further. From the alcoholic extract a crystalline substance was obtained, which from its analysis and other properties appears to be gluco-nonitol. Occurrence of gluco-nonitol, a synthetic product so far, in nature is a matter of considerable interest. Besides fatty and resinous matter, nothing crystalline could be isolated from the water-soluble portion of the alcoholic extract; but in the water-insoluble portion three crystalline acids were found to be present: the one, occurring in the largest amount (0.3%) on the leaves is *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid; the second acid appears to be 5-oxy-*isophthalic* acid and the third acid has been identified as 3:4-dioxybenzoic acid. Besides the above crystalline acids a fair amount of tannic acid is also present. From the basic lead acetate precipitate, an amorphous glucoside has been isolated, which is very soluble in water and yields *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid, glucose and a dark brown amorphous substance on hydrolysis with hot acids or with sodium ethylate. Examination of the fresh flush of leaves, collected in February and March, revealed the presence of a different micro-crystalline glucoside, sparingly soluble in cold water and dilute mineral acids (about 2%), or even by boiling with water alone, it breaks up into *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid, glucose and a dark brown (almost black) amorphous substance. Hydrolysis with ice-cold

alcoholic sulphuric acid (5%), however, yields glucose and two amorphous substances, one of them being acidic and the other neutral in reaction. Both of these hydrolysis products, on being boiled with sulphuric acid (2%) yields *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid and the same dark brown amorphous substance, as in the case of the original glucoside. Hydrolysis with alcoholic potash, on the other hand, yields *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid and a second crystalline glucoside, which on further hydrolysis with cold dilute sulphuric acid (5% alcoholic) breaks up into glucose and a yellow brown amorphous substance. Further work to elucidate the composition of this substance is in hand. Tentatively the formula $C_{20}H_{24}O_{11}$ is being given to the original glucoside and $C_{13}H_{20}O_9$ to the second glucoside, which is its alkali hydrolysis product. Thus the two glucosides, one isolated from mature leaves and the other from the fresh flush of leaves, although they differ considerably in their properties, appear to be closely related in so far that both on hot acid hydrolysis yield *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid, glucose and a dark brown amorphous substance.

As regards the physiological properties of the leaves, their germicidal action appears to be due to the presence of *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid. The glucoside has been sent to the Department of Pharmacology, School of Tropical Medicine, Calcutta, for determination of its physiological properties. Preliminary examination has shown it to be physiologically active. A detailed report will be published in due course.

EXPERIMENTAL

Mature Leaves Collected in September and October.

Extraction of the Leaves with Alcohol.—Several kg. of the powdered leaves were extracted by percolation with cold alcohol (90-94%). Bulk of the alcohol was removed by distillation under reduced pressure and the concentrated extract allowed to stand for 3-4 days, when some crystals (1) separated. From the filtrate, alcohol was removed completely and the residue was extracted with hot water. The insoluble matter, which contained fatty and resinous matter, was examined further, but nothing crystalline was obtained. The filtered aqueous extract was concentrated to a syrup under reduced pressure and repeatedly extracted with ether. The ether extract was concentrated and repeatedly extracted with small quantities of sodium carbonate solution. On removal of the ether a small quantity of a brown resinous substance remained which was not examined further.

The dark yellow sodium carbonate solution was acidified with sulphuric acid, saturated with common salt and repeatedly extracted with ether. On removal of the ether, the free acids (II) came out as a dark brown crystalline mass.

The concentrated aqueous solution, after being extracted with ether, was diluted to thrice its volume and lead acetate solution was added when a deep yellow precipitate (III) was obtained. To the filtrate and washing basic lead acetate was added, when a canary yellow precipitate (IV) was obtained. The filtrate was freed from lead and examined but nothing crystalline was obtained. It only gave reactions of sugar.

Gluco-nonitol.—The crystalline substance (I) was found to be readily soluble in water but practically insoluble in absolute alcohol. It was recrystallised thrice from dilute alcohol when it came out as perfect white needles, m.p. 196-98°. It does not reduce Fehling's solution. It is very slightly dextro-rotatory, $[\alpha]^{20}_D = +1.5^\circ$; (6.6% aqueous solution). (Found: C, 39.9; H 7.5. $C_9H_{20}O_9$ requires C, 39.7; H, 7.4 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative, prepared with acetic anhydride and freshly fused zinc chloride, crystallised from ethyl acetate and finally from absolute alcohol, m.p. 179-80°, yield 3.2 g. from 2.5 g. [Found: C, 49.9; H, 6.2. $C_9H_{11}O_9 (CH_3CO)_9$ requires C, 49.8; H, 5.8 per cent]. On saponification with caustic potash 0.5280 g. of the substance gave 0.430 g. of acetic acid *i.e.*, 81% on the weight of the substance. $C_9H_{11}O_9 (CH_3CO)_9$ should yield 83% of its weight of acetic acid.

Lead acetate precipitate (III).—It was decomposed with sulphuretted hydrogen. Lead and H_2S were removed and the aqueous solution was concentrated to a small bulk under reduced pressure, and then extracted repeatedly with ether. The ethereal solution was extracted several times with sodium carbonate solution and the latter acidified and again extracted with ether, the ether was removed, when a crystalline magma (IIIa) was obtained. The concentrated aqueous solution after extraction with ether, was examined but nothing besides tannic acid could be detected.

Free Acids.—The crystalline acidic substance (II) crystallised from hot water as prismatic needles, m.p. 208-9°. These crystals gave greenish blue colour with ferric chloride, a precipitate with lead acetate and a copious light yellow precipitate with basic lead acetate. The mother liquor also gave a deep greenish blue colour with ferric chloride

and a precipitate with lead acetate. The crystalline magma (IIIa) also behaved in the same way. The two crystalline magmas (II) and (IIIa) were, therefore, combined, dissolved in boiling water and filtered from insoluble resins. The clear solution was then treated with lead acetate. The light yellow precipitate (IIIb) was removed and examined separately. The filtrate was delead and evaporated to a small bulk when stout prismatic needles, m.p. $210-11^{\circ}$, were obtained, which when recrystallised from water (charcoal) melted at $215-16^{\circ}$.

The properties and analysis showed that it is probably *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid, and this was confirmed by preparation of the ethyl ester (m.p. $115-16^{\circ}$), the *methoxy* derivative (m.p. $181-82^{\circ}$, mixed m.p.) and tribromophenol (m.p. $93-94^{\circ}$, mixed m.p.) (Found: C, 60.86; H, 4.75. Calc. for $C_7H_6O_3$: C, 60.87; H, 4.35 per cent).

5-Oxy-isophthalic Acid.—The lead acetate precipitate (IIIb) was suspended in water and decomposed with sulphuretted hydrogen. On removal of sulphuretted hydrogen and concentration on water-bath crystals separated which were recrystallised from hot water, m.p. $285-87^{\circ}$. The substance was very sparingly soluble in cold water, readily soluble in boiling water, alcohol and ether. It gave a yellow brown colour with ferric chloride and white precipitate with lead acetate and silver nitrate. It sublimed and heated with lime it gave off phenol. It appears that this acid is *5-oxy-isophthalic acid* (m.p. 288°). The quantity isolated, however, was too small for definite characterisation.

3:4-Dioxybenzoic Acid.—After removal of the above acid and concentration of the mother-liquor almost to a syrup and allowing it to stand for some days a crystalline magma was obtained, which was drained on porous plate and recrystallised from benzene and alcohol. Recrystallised from a very small quantity of water it was obtained as faintly yellow needles, m.p. $197-98^{\circ}$.

The analysis and properties all agree with *3:4-dioxybenzoic acid*. (Found: C, 54.8; H, 3.7. Calc. for $C_7H_6O_4$: C, 54.5; H, 3.7 per cent).

Amorphous Glucoside.—The basic lead acetate precipitate (IV) was decomposed with sulphuretted hydrogen. The filtrate, after removal of lead and H_2S , was made just neutral, concentrated to a small bulk under reduced pressure, acidified and extracted with ether, which removed some *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid. The aqueous solution was neutralised and further concentrated to a thick syrup under reduced pressure. It was then absorbed in filter paper, dried and extracted in a Soxhlet with methyl alcohol, the extract was concentrated, but no crystals separated. It was then poured on to acetone, filtered and the

yellow solution decolourised, the solvent removed and the residue dried. A light brown amorphous substance was obtained (0.74% on leaves) which was very soluble in water and alcohol, less soluble in acetone and ethyl acetate and insoluble in ether, chloroform and petroleum ether. It was purified by solution in alcohol and precipitation by ether, m.p. 93-95°. It did not reduce Fehling's solution but did so after hydrolysis with dilute sulphuric acid. The pure glucoside did not give any precipitate with lead acetate nor any colour with ferric chloride.

On hydrolysis with sulphuric acid (5%) on a water-bath for 6 hours, a dark brown amorphous substance separated. It was extracted with ether, which did not dissolve the dark brown substance. From the ether extract crystals were obtained which recrystallised from water (m. p. 215-16°) and was proved to be *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid. The acidic solution, after removal of the dark brown substance and *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid, was found to contain only glucose (phenylsazone, m.p. 208°).

2.3 G. of the glucoside was dissolved in methyl alcohol (10 c.c.) and sodium (0.2 g.) dissolved in methyl alcohol (10 c.c.) was added and the whole heated on a water-bath for 3 hours. Alcohol was removed and the residue dissolved in water, the clear reddish brown solution was acidified with sulphuric acid and extracted with ether, the ether removed and *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid was obtained. From the solution after extraction with ether, nothing excepting glucose could be detected.

Fresh Flush of Leaves Collected in February and March.

Alcoholic Extract of the Leaves.—As before the air-dried leaves were extracted with alcohol by cold percolation. From the concentrated alcoholic extract crystals of gluco-nonitol were removed and the filtrate was freed from alcohol. The residue was extracted with boiling water, filtered and allowed to stand overnight. A voluminous greenish-blue crystalline magma separated. This was never noticed before in the case of mature leaves. The substance was sparingly soluble in cold water, fairly soluble in hot water and in 90% alcohol and insoluble in ether and chloroform. Preliminary examination showed it to be a glucoside. After removal of this glucoside, the filtrate was examined for free acids; only *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid and 3,4-dioxybenzoic acid were found to be present.

The Glucoside present in the Fresh Flush of Leaves.—The crude glucoside was purified by solution in pyridine and fractional precipitation with chloroform, yield 2.2% on the leaves, m.p. 152-53° (decomp.). It was further purified by solution in alcohol and fractional precipitation with ether; a yellow-brown colouring matter was first precipitated and then the glucoside. Repeating the operation thrice an almost colourless microcrystalline substance was obtained, m. p. 154-55°; $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -92.6^\circ$ (3.23% absolute alcoholic solution). It is neutral in reaction and is very sensitive to heat and mineral acids. Heated with dilute mineral acids and even with acetic acid it breaks up into *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid, sugar and a dark brown (almost black) amorphous substance, which is insoluble in water, only partly so in alcohol or acetone and insoluble in most organic solvents. Even at ordinary temperature (25°) dilute mineral acids slowly decompose the glucoside into the above substances. It is similarly decomposed by prolonged boiling with water. It does not give any precipitate with lead acetate but gives a copious white precipitate with basic lead acetate. It gives a reddish violet colour with ferric chloride.

Acid Hydrolysis of the Glucoside.—The glucoside (5 g.) in alcohol (50 c.c.) was cooled in ice, and ice-cold sulphuric acid (2.5 c.c. in 10 c.c. water, 10 c.c.) added and the mixture kept in a thermoflask in ice for 7 days. The green solution was poured on to ether, ether decanted off and the aqueous layer was washed with ether thrice. The combined ethereal solution was extracted repeatedly with sodium carbonate solution, the ether removed when a viscous, light brown substance (A) (about 24% of the glucoside) was obtained. From the ice-cold alkali solution, acidified with sulphuric acid, ether extracted an acidic substance (B) which was also amorphous and varnish-like (about 34% of the glucoside). The original green aqueous acid solution was found to contain only sugar (about 42%) (phenylosazone, m.p. 208-9°).

The neutral substance (A) was purified by solution in ether and pouring into petroleum ether. All attempts to crystallise the light brown viscous precipitate failed. Further hydrolysis by boiling with dilute sulphuric acid resulted in the formation of the dark brown amorphous substance and *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid. No sugar was present. The acidic substance (B) was purified in the same way. It was also an amorphous substance of light brown colour which would not crystallise. Hydrolysed with alcoholic sulphuric acid (5%) on a water-bath for 4 hours it gave *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid (35% of its

weight) and the same dark brown substance. Hydrolysed with sodium ethylate in alcoholic solution, it also gave *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid (34.4%) and a dark yellow-brown neutral substance which would not crystallise. This neutral substance readily absorbed bromine and gave a crystalline bromo compound insoluble in cold water, readily soluble in alcohol and ether. Recrystallised from ether it was obtained as long needles, m.p. 92-93°. Further work is in progress to determine the nature of this substance.

Alkali Hydrolysis of the Glucoside.—The purified glucoside (10 g.) was hydrolysed with alcoholic potash (100 c.c., 5%) on a water-bath for 6 hours. Alcohol was removed and the residue dissolved in a small quantity of water, cooled in ice, acidified and extracted with ether. On removal of ether *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid was obtained. The aqueous solution was neutralised and evaporated to dryness and the residue was extracted in a Soxhlet with alcohol, the alcoholic extract, decolourised and bulk of the alcohol removed and a little ether added till slightly opalescent crystalline needles came out. These were recrystallised from ether-alcohol, m.p. 173-74°. It is readily soluble in cold water. It does not give any precipitate with either, lead acetate or basic lead acetate and no colour with ferric chloride. On being further hydrolysed by dilute sulphuric acid, it gives a dark brown amorphous substance and glucose but no *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid. It has $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -163.6^\circ$ (5.136% aqueous solution) and M.W., 310. It is, therefore, a second glucoside formed from the original glucoside by the splitting off of *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid from its molecule by alkali. The glucose content of this substance, as estimated by Fehling's solution, is about 58%. Further hydrolysis of this product with alcoholic sulphuric acid (5%) at about 12° for 24 hours gave glucose and a deep yellow-brown amorphous substance, neutral in reaction, insoluble in water, but readily soluble in ether and alcohol. The nature of this substance is being investigated.

The original glucoside was found to contain about 42% of glucose (Found: C, 54.9; H, 5.6; M.W., 429. $C_{20}H_{24}O_{11}$ requires C, 54.5; H, 5.5 per cent. M.W., 440). The second glucoside should, therefore, have a formula $C_{13}H_{20}O_9$. (Found: C, 48.7; H, 5.8. $C_{13}H_{20}O_9$ requires C, 48.8; H, 6.2 per cent). The molecular weight, as found from its sugar content, is also in close agreement.